

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF VERB FORMS IN FRENCH AND URDU LANGUAGES

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Abstract

Taking reference from French grammar, this paper proposes a new structure of verb forms in Urdu grammar. It argues that classifying verbs in moods before classifying them in tenses, as in Urdu grammar, misses many meanings that verbs carry in any sentence. To find the moods in Urdu, it examines the endings of the conjugation of different tenses in Urdu and their functions. It takes then examples from French verb forms and applies them to Urdu verb forms. This comparison leads to a striking resemblance in the verb forms of both languages. It makes Urdu one step closer to romance languages such as French, Spanish, and Italian, where verbs take mood before tense. It suggests, too, that mood precedes tense. Every verb in a sentence does not necessarily take a tense, and no verb in a sentence exists without a mood. In the end, this paper suggests renaming مضارع, a tense in the Urdu language, and splitting two other tenses ماضى شرطيه and ماضى احتمالى into four tenses.

Keywords: Urdu, French, mood, subjunctive, grammar, verb forms, مضارع, ماضى شرطيه, ماضى احتمالى, tenses,

Introduction

Students of French as a Foreign Language get to know the concept of mood very early in their language learning journey, a form of verb hardly known to students in advance. Does this mean this concept does not exist in languages they are familiar with, or does it exist but is yet to be discovered? A similar problem occurs while teaching Urdu as a Foreign Language to French native speakers who tend to associate tenses in their mother tongue with those in the Urdu language. Most students I have been teaching French speak Urdu as their mother tongue. Does the concept of mood exist in Urdu grammar? It was only during a lecture explaining the

subjunctive mood in French that the idea of looking at the classification of verbs in Urdu popped up to see if one such mood existed there.

So far as the English language is concerned, it classifies verbs in three moods: indicative, subjunctive, and imperative, before classifying them in tenses. However, for two reasons, one does not need to pay much attention to the subjunctive mood while learning English as a Foreign Language. Firstly, using verbs in the subjunctive mood is rare in English, and the indicative mood replaces it comfortably. Secondly, a verb in English does not have a unique form in the subjunctive mood; the present subjunctive takes the verb's infinitive form, and the past subjunctive takes its simple past form. In 'I wish I were wealthier,' 'were' is a subjunctive. In sentences such as 'It is advisable that the principal resign' and 'I suggest that he take a short nap,' verbs 'resign' and 'take' are in the subjunctive mood. Nevertheless, these sentences can take the indicative mood. 'It is advisable that the principal should resign' and 'I suggest that he should take a short nap' will be the new sentences.

Urdu does not classify verbs according to mood. Maulvi Abdul Haq, an eminent scholar of Urdu, popularly known as 'Baba-e-Urdu, mentions five moods ("Qawaed-e-Urdu", 100). He does not associate those moods with different verb forms, but with possible functions, different verb forms can serve. When French takes moods, it means both, a unique verb form for different tenses in different moods and a unique sense. Does a similar structure exist in Urdu? In search of the answer to this question, this paper analyses all tenses in Urdu, which leads to some new findings. Firstly, unlike in French, where one ending of a verb denotes one tense, in Urdu, in some cases, various endings of a verb denote one tense. Such is the case with ماضی شرطیہ and ماضی ناتمام، ماضی احتمالی. Does this mean using one of these forms will help discover a new tense? Secondly, a tense named مضارع is also a source of trouble. Having considered it under the present tense, Urdu grammarians are not very sure as to which tense it should be associated with: present, past, or future. These two phenomena will be the basis on which this paper will count for much of its findings.

Urdu Grammar

Undoubtedly, Urdu was born in India. It was formed with a blend of Prakrit and Persian, taking words from Sanskrit and Arabic in different stages of its development. Though many foreign languages left their impacts on its nouns and adjectives, major building blocks came primarily

from its original language. Its subject pronouns, object pronouns, possessive adjectives, possessive pronouns, and almost all verbs came from there. (Abdul Haq, 8-9). However, Urdu borrowed from Arabic through Persian terms for science and technology, including those defining the features of the language. Is the original meaning of مضارع in Arabic a source of problem in Urdu? Does a language with a limited number of tenses fail to accommodate a language with a more significant number of verbs, resulting in assigning various endings to one single tense, as is the case with ماضی شرطیہ and ماضی ناتمام، ماضی احتمالی?

Before proceeding to our principal question, it is essential to remember that Urdu literature has attracted extensive research, but its grammar has received different attention. It might have enjoyed less popularity to attract people worldwide to learn Urdu as a Foreign Language. Native speakers, in general, do not need grammar. That is why those who paid first attention to Urdu grammar were scholars associated with the East India Company, including Joshua Kettler, a Dutch ambassador to India, and John Borthwick Gilchrist, a Scottish Indologist. Insha Ullah Khan was one of the first Urdu scholars to write on Urdu grammar in Darya-e-Latafat, a book that includes prose, poems, and sociolects spoken by women of his time. (Abdul Haq, 14-16). Currently, two books are prevalent among Urdu students. They are Qawaed-e-Urdu and Urd Sarf-o-Nahv, written by Maulvi Abdul Haq. This paper will take many references from these books.

Classification of Verbs Forms in Urdu

A first review of how Urdu grammarians classify verb forms looks essential. When Abdul Haq takes on verb forms, he distributes them in present, past, and future and does not associate verb forms with any moods. He distributes the past tense in six tenses: the simple past (ماضی مطلق), the recent past (ماضی قریب), the past perfect (ماضی بعید), the past continuous (ماضی استمراری), the conditional past (ماضی شرطیہ) and one more tense that he calls ماضی احتمالی. The last two tenses demand particular deliberation. He subdivides the present tense into five tenses; he names the first tense مضارع, another tense that needs greater attention in this paper. The next tense is the imperative (امر), which requires a different place in this distribution. The remaining three tenses are the simple present (حال مطلق), the present continuous (حال ناتمام), and حال احتمالی. He distributes the future tense in two tenses: future simple (مستقبل مطلق) and future continuous (مستقبل مدامی).

While comparing this distribution, some questions arose. Though most of the verb forms looked suitably positioned, the place of مضارع does not seem to be in the present tense. Should the imperative form of the verb in Urdu (امر) not be treated separately? How do we deal with various verb forms of single tenses, as is the case in ماضى، ماضى احتمالى، and حال احتمالى? شرطيه?

A case for مضارع

مضارع is one of six tenses of the present tense in Urdu. It is formed by removing نا from the infinitive and adding these endings. ے، ئیں، و، ئیں. ں، ئیں.

If we take the verb لانا, the conjugation (گردان) of مضارع will be as

وہ لائے، وہ لائیں، تم لاؤ، آپ لائیں، میں لاؤں، ہم لائیں
تم کچھ نہ لاؤ تو بہتر ہے

So far as the word مضارع is concerned, it comes from the Arabic word المضارع, which denotes a form of verbs used to express a set of tenses. In the Arabic language, the word المضارع means something similar. Arab grammarians named a verb المضارع as it resembles nouns in many ways and also because it englobes present and future tenses (Siraj al-Din, 81-82). The Urdu grammarians have named مضارع due to its resemblance to the simple present tense in Urdu. While trying to accommodate مضارع among the present tenses, Abdul Haq says: "مضارع is the simplest form of the present tense. However, its present forms do not express the present tense clearly. Urdu grammarians have counted مضارع as a verb apart and excluded it from present, past, and future. This exclusion is not correct, as no verb exists without any tense. It is a present tense and includes the meaning of the present tense" (Translation by Iqbal Ahmed, "Qawaid-e-Urdu" 106).

While explaining its use, Abdul Haq says مضارع expresses various functions in Urdu that are difficult to incorporate into grammar. One can acquire the correct use only through study and conversations. Then, he enumerates a few situations to explain the use of مضارع.

1. In colloquial and daily use sentences in the meaning of the present tense as in کمائیں ہم اور اڑائیں وہ.

2. In conditional sentences with the meaning of doubt, as in مینہ برسے تے کہیتی ہری بو
3. To take permission in some cases, as in آپ فرمائیں تو آؤں
4. For wish and blessings as in خدا کرے وہ کامیاب ہو جائے
5. To express surprise, astonishment as in وہ اور ایسا کرے
6. In the subordinate after کاف بیانیہ with the condition that the main clause contains expressions like شاید بشرطیکہ، and expresses purpose, will, wish, needs, advice, result, command and similar expressions as in مناسب یہ ہے کہ وہ وہاں نہ جائے، ہنر تو یہ کہ ہم ساتھ چلیں
7. To express confusion and doubt as in کیا کروں، کیا نہ کروں Translation by Iqbal Ahmed, "Urdu Sar-o- Nahw", 55-56)

If we look closely, it clearly shows that مضارع indeed functions to express the present tense. Nevertheless, something distinguishes it from other present tenses as it does not express a habit, any action in progress right now, or from any point of time in the past.

In the search for what distinguishes مضارع from other present tenses, this paper finds some answers with Abdul Haq. While explaining the intrinsic features of verbs, Maulvi Abdul Haq mentions their transitive and intransitive nature, their distribution in present, past, and future tenses, and their use in active and passive voice. Then, he talks of one characteristic of verb forms that he names صورت and says that five types of صورت exist in Urdu to describe a verb. He names them as خبری، شرطی، مصدری، امری، احتمالی (Translation by Iqbal Ahmed, "Qawaid-e-Urdu" 100).

What exactly Abdul Haq means by صورت is unclear as he is silent and tries to explain صورت by its attributes. It seems he is talking about what French Grammarians call moods. In grammar, as *Le Robert* mentions, mood is the characteristic of a verb that explains the speaker's attitude towards his words.¹ This definition of moods keeps it above the tense. If the speaker informs about a person, thing, or event, his attitude towards that will differ from when he asks someone to do something or talks of hypothetical events. These primary lines guide the grammarians in classifying verbs in different moods.

¹ <https://dictionnaire.lerobert.com/guide/indicatif> Accessed 5 May, 2024

The following sentences in French make the difference between moods clear. Je suis sûr qu'il viendra (I am sure he will come). Je ne suis pas sûr qu'il vienne (I am not sure he will come). In these examples, the subordinate clause in the French sentence takes the verb in the indicative mood after the principal clause in the affirmative case and the subjunctive mood after the principal clause in the negative case. When the speaker is sure, the verb is in the indicative mood, and when the person is unsure, the verb is in the subjunctive mood. This difference is not visible in the English language. Both clauses are in the indicative mood in the English sentence. An overlapping exists between English and French in the subjunctive mood. It is much more frequent in French than it is in English. It is also worth mentioning that what is meant by verbs in different moods and tenses is a given form of the verb and not necessarily the purpose a verb serves in any sentence. A verb in the past tense may sometimes express the sense of the present tense, and both the imperative and indicative mood pass on the sense of command.

There are seven moods in French: indicative, subjunctive, conditional, imperative, infinitive, present, and past participle (Poisson-Quintin, 355). Similar terms used for the types of sentences should not be the source of confusion, as sentences are also declarative, interrogative, imperative, and exclamatory.

As the following lines will clarify, traces are available to prove that Urdu grammarians have attempted to describe moods but stopped somewhere in the midway. As mentioned earlier, Abdul Haq mentions five types of moods. He names the first mood خبری صورت. For him, it gives information of any event or interrogates any matter as in آپ پانی پئیں گے؟ and حامد گر پڑا. On similar lines, Le Robert, a French dictionary, says the indicative mood enunciates, in a natural way, a statement considered true and confirmed in an affirmative sentence and a statement that needs verification in an interrogative sentence. This mood indicates the moment of action and helps situate the statement in time. It is the mood of objectivity. The indicative mood covers all the axes of time as in '*Il pleut maintenant*' (It is raining right now) or '*Comment vas-tu?*' (How are you?)

When compared, both of them give definitions of the same thing: the indicative mood. As مضارع does not give information about any event or interrogate any matter independently without its main clause, including مضارع in the indicative mood does not go well. However, the indicative

mood is vast as it covers all twelve tenses in English. In French, it consists of one tense in the present (le présent), five tenses in the past (le passé composé, le passé simple, l'imparfait, le plus-que-parfait, le passé antérieur) and two tenses in the future (le futur simple, le futur antérieur). Which tenses will be part of the indicative mood in Urdu will be seen at the end of this article.

A name change suggestion seems required. Though خبری صورت in Urdu is the same thing as the indicative mood in French, the term خبری صورت for the indicative mood in Urdu does not suit well. The term اشارتی صورت may convey the message in a better way for two reasons. Firstly, اشارہ and indication have the same meaning, which makes it closer to similar terms in other languages. Secondly, in the Urdu language, جملہ خبریہ is the declarative sentence. The declarative sentence and the indicative mood are not the same things. The first is the characteristics of a sentence, and the second is the characteristics of a verb.

The following mood in French is the subjunctive mood. It is the mood of subjectivity. It enunciates an unfinished or uncertain action, and the speaker needs to refrain from engaging in this mood. The subjunctive mood interprets things and appreciates realities. That is why it only needs some axes of the time. In French, it includes one tense in the present (le subjonctif présent), three tenses in the past (le subjonctif passé, le subjonctif imparfait, le subjonctif plus-que-parfait). It does not include any tense in the future. A verb takes the subjunctive mood subject to three conditions. Firstly, it takes the subordinate clause and not the main clause. Taking an independent sentence is rare for the subjunctive mood. If it does, it is in the exclamatory sentences, as in 'Que le meilleur gagne!' (May the best win!). Secondly, it follows expressions of doubt, will, order, wish, and other emotions. Thirdly, the subjects of the primary and subordinate clauses must not refer to the same person. Here are two examples from French in the present subjunctive mood with their translation in Urdu. A comparison of these verbs shows that they both express the same functions in their respective languages.

Je voudrais que vous veniez à l'heure. (میں چاہتا ہوں کہ آپ وقت پر تشریف لائیں)

Je cherche quelqu'un qui puisse m'aider. (میں کسی ایسے کی تلاش میں ہوں جو (میری مدد کر سکے)

The French verbs ‘veniez’ and ‘puisse’ are in the subjunctive moods as Urdu verbs ‘کر سکے’ and (لائیں) مضارع.

This comparison shows that it is not the tense that varies in both languages but the relation of these verbs with their speakers because both sentences are in the present tense. It means adding a new mood (صورت) in the Urdu language will resolve the confusion raised by Abdul Haq regarding the position of مضارع in the present tense. That mood is the subjunctive mood.

This new mood must take a name in Urdu-none of the five moods Abdul Haq mentions fit here. Though مضارع expresses doubt in many cases, the phrase احتمالی صورت will not serve the purpose either, as مضارع comes in the subordinate clause (تابع جملہ) and not in the independent clauses. A Google translation of the subjunctive moods in Urdu suggests ضمنی مزاج, out of which taking ضمنی can make ضمنی صورت. However, this paper names it الحاقی صورت as this name suits better to express the functions of the subjunctive mood. The subjunctive word in English comes from the French word *subjonctif*, which has come from the Latin verb *subjungere*, which means to bind, assemble, and harness. The subordinate clause that uses the subjunctive mood is bound and harnessed to its main clause. The word الحاق in Arabic gives a very similar meaning.

After establishing مضارع as a member of a new mood in the Urdu language, suggesting a modification in its name seems feasible. Most readers would not welcome a modification of this type as the convention rules in these cases. However, this paper suggests that this modification will make it closer to its new mood and tense. Naming it حال ملحق after الحاقی صورت may not shock readers. Another reason why this paper advocates for this name is that it rhymes well with the word مطلق in the tense حال مطلق.

ماضی ملحق

After discovering a new tense in Urdu حال ملحق, which is almost equivalent to the subjunctive present in French, seeking a verb in Urdu that would be equivalent to the subjunctive past in French does not look like an adventure. Most teachers of Urdu as a Foreign Language refer to مضارع as the only tense in the subjunctive mood, as does Rajiv Ranjan in an open

book on Urdu.² In this search, this paper looks at the tenses with one name and multiple verb forms.

One such tense is ماضی احتمالی. For example, the verb آنا takes two conjugations in this tense. The first form is :

وہ آیا ہوگا، وہ آئی ہوگی، وہ آئے ہونگے
تو آیا ہوگا، تو آئی ہوگی، تم آئے ہوگے، آپ آئے ہونگے
میں آیا ہونگا، میں آئی نگے، ہم آئے ہونگے

The second form is:

وہ آیا ہو، وہ آئی ہو، وہ آئے ہوں
تو آیا ہو، تو آئی ہو، تم آئے ہو، آپ آئے ہوں
میں آیا ہوں، میں آئی ہوں، ہم آئے ہوں

While mentioning these two forms, Abdul Haq says the second form of this tense expresses a higher degree of probability than the first form ("Urdu Sar-o- Nahw," 54). The degree of variance apart, the paper argues that the first form takes the independent sentence, and the second takes the subordinate clause. This way, it fulfills the conditions required for the use of a verb in ملحق or حال ملحق (مضارع). Thus, this tense is equal to the subjunctive past in French. Urdu can name it ماضی ملحق. Here is an example.

ممکن ہے کہ وہ نہ آیا ہو
نہیں، وہ ضرور آیا ہوگا

In this example, the first form is the subordinate clause, and the second is the independent form. The independent verb form is ماضی احتمالی, and the verb form which is subordinate to the principal clause is ماضی ملحق. The following two examples make clear that both tenses are part of the subjunctive mood.

(حال ملحق) ممکن ہے وہ بیمار ہو
(ماضی ملحق) ممکن ہے وہ ٹھیک ہو گیا ہو

² [8.9 Subjunctive Mood – Basic Urdu \(msu.edu\)](https://msu.edu/8.9-Subjunctive-Mood-Basic-Urdu), Accessed 5 May. 2024

A Case for امر

One more verb form that has not found its respective place in the distribution of verbs is the imperative form of the verb. Abdul Haq considers it in the present tense without considering any mood. It fits perfectly in امری صورت, a mood he mentions but does not elaborate on. Looking at purely on the meaning, a verb in the امری صورت can replace the same verb in the subjunctive present.

(امری صورت or the imperative mood) آپ یہاں نہ ٹھہریے

(حال ملحق or the subjunctive present) میں چاہتا ہوں کہ آپ یہاں نہ ٹھہریں

In French, the imperative mood, however, takes two tenses; one is called the imperative present, and the other is called the imperative past. The imperative past in French commands something before a given time. A similar situation in Urdu with a form of a verb other than that of امر remains a subject of intrigue.

A Case for حال شرطیہ

The next tense, which has two types of conjugation and one single form, is ماضی شرطیہ. What is surprising is that Urdu grammarians do not mention any tense named حال شرطیہ. On the contrary, the French language, however, has both the conditional present and conditional past. The French conditional tenses express many functions, including hope, request, and conditions. The following lines compare the two forms of ماضی شرطیہ.

As an example, the verb آنا takes two conjugations in this tense.

The first form is:

وہ آتا، وہ آتی، وہ آتے
تو آتا، تو آتی، تم آتے، آپ آتے
میں آتا، میں آتی، ہم آتے

The second form is:

وہ آیا ہوتا، وہ آئی ہوتی، وہ آئے ہوتے
تو آیا ہوتا، تو آئی ہوتی، تم آئے ہوتے، آپ آئے ہوتے
میں آیا ہوتا، میں آئی ہوتی، ہم آئے ہوتے

The fundamental question that needs an answer is whether these two forms express the same thing without referencing a time gap.

اگر وہ آجاتا تو اچھا ہوتا

اگر تم محنت کئے ہوتے تو اچھا روزگار پائے ہوتے

A close look at these two sentences confirms they do not refer to the same point in time. Does this mean *ماضی شرطیہ* can split into two tenses *حال شرطیہ* and *ماضی شرطیہ*? As this needs further digging, one point is confirmed. Whether to take them as one tense or two, these tenses will come under the conditional mood in the list of *صورت* by Abdul Haq, leading to *شرطی صورت*.

احتمالی صورت A Case for

So far as *احتمالی صورت* matters, no equivalent of this mood is present in the French language. However, both conditional and subjunctive moods express the sense of doubt and probability. Abdul Haq defines *احتمالی صورت* as a form of the verb that expresses doubt. The following sentences expressed this clearly.

(یہ خط) اسی نے لکھا ہوگا. مومکن ہے کہ وہ نہ گیا ہو. شاید وہ آجائے

If we translate these three sentences into French, they will take three different tenses. (C'est lui qui aurait écrit cette lettre. Il est possible qu'il ne soit pas allé. Il est probable qu'il vienne.) The three sentences have been translated into French using verbs in the conditional past, subjunctive past, and subjunctive present, respectively. If we look at the tenses of these verbs in Urdu, the first sentence is in *ماضی احتمالی*, the second sentence is *حال ملحق (مضارع)*, and the last sentence is in *ماضی ملحق*.

This article claims from the beginning that Abdul Haq mentioned different moods of verbs but did not mean any specific forms of verbs directly linked by any of these moods. So, he does not give necessarily examples from tenses that he would later call *ماضی احتمالی* or *حال احتمالی* to express the sense of doubt. He believes different tenses can express the sense of doubt; otherwise, he would have given examples from tenses with which he associated the term *احتمالی*.

Distribution of Verbs in Moods in Urdu Language

After looking at the functions of different verb forms, this paper classifies them along the lines Maulvi Abdul Haq mentioned in his book Qawaed-e-Urdu with some new suggestions. This paper suggests to keep ten tenses of present, past and future with اشارتی صورت (the indicative mood), the same mood that Abdul Haq names خبری صورت. These tenses are ماضی، مطلق، ماضی قریب، ماضی بعید، ماضی استمراری، ماضی ناتمام، حال مطلق، حال ناتمام، مستقبل مطلق مستقبل مدامی

Classifying the remaining verb forms along the same lines is not feasible. Abdul Haq includes فعل امر in the list of present tenses. This paper gives it a new mood امری صورت, as do grammarians in other languages. Abdul Haq considers مضارع along with other present tenses. This paper keeps it in a different mood altogether that it names الحاقی صورت, and it proposes to change the name of مضارع to حال ملحق. Abdul Haq keeps two different verb forms under ماضی احتمالی. This paper splits them into ماضی احتمالی and ماضی ملحق, thus associating the latter with الحاقی صورت (the subjunctive mood). It suggests adding ماضی شرطیہ to حال شرطیہ to make them two tenses while keeping them along the lines of Abdul Haq in the شرطی صورت.

Here are two tables, one with moods table in French and another with proposed moods table in Urdu with different tenses associated with different moods.

Moods Table in French

Indicatif	Subjonctif	Conditionnel	Impératif	Infinitif	Participe
Présent	Présent	Présent	Impératif	Infinitif Présent	Présent
Passé composé	Passé	Passé		Infinitif Passé	Passé
Passé simple
Imparfait	Imparfait
Plus-que- parfait	Plus-que- parfait

Passé antérieur
Futur
Futur antérieur

Proposed Moods Table in Urdu

مصدری	امری	الحاقی	احتمالی	شرطی	اشارتی
مصدر	امر	ماضی ملحق	ماضی احتمالی	ماضی شرطیہ	ماضی مطلق
.....	ماضی قریب
.....	ماضی بعید
.....	ماضی استمراری
.....	ماضی ناتمام
.....	(مضارع) حال ملحق	حال احتمالی	حال شرطیہ	حال مطلق
.....	حال ناتمام
.....	مستقبل مطلق
.....	مستقبل مدامی

Conclusion

The distribution of verb forms in moods before doing so in tenses in the Urdu language, as shown in this paper, will help understand various nuances of verb forms in the Urdu language. As the subject is related to French and Urdu, a more elaborate study is due and need of time. It will make this article more purposeful and accessible. A more comprehensive

study is still needed as most of the examples in this article come from Maulvi Abdul Haq's books.

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